

IS AUTHENTIC LEARNING EFFECTIVE TO IMPLEMENT IN THE INDONESIAN CURRICULUM??

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Abstract: *In the 21st century, students need the ability to solve real-life problems, namely those encountered in society outside of school, which cannot be solved by simply memorizing material. These skills can be honed through the use of the Authentic Learning method, because in this method, students are given problems that can be encountered in real life and are encouraged to independently use HOTS (High Order Thinking Skills). With the change in the Indonesian curriculum, which is considered to lack thorough preparation in its implementation, as well as the variety of methods used and outputs that cannot be considered satisfactory, this raises the question: will the Authentic Learning model be effective if applied to the Indonesian curriculum, considering that many developed countries, such as Finland, Japan, and the United States, have already implemented this method? This article was written using a qualitative approach, namely the collection of information through literature research, books, journals, and institutional archives. Much of the information in this article is sourced from journals, articles, or literature reviews that are relevant to the topic. Authentic learning can be understood as a learning process carried out using methods and in an environment that correspond to “real” experiences in students' lives, both inside and outside the classroom. Meanwhile, PJBL focuses on achieving targets through activities such as designing, testing, or implementing a product or project. In contrast, PBL provides more space for exploration, creativity, in-depth investigation, and requires students to take control of their learning process independently. Through additional distinctions, Authentic Learning involves complex communication such as persuading, explaining, conveying, and negotiating in solving complex problems through collaboration.*

Keywords: *Authentic Learning, PJBL, PBL, Curriculum.*

INTRODUCTION

The learning models recently used in Indonesia are Merdeka Curriculum and Curriculum 2013. (Martatiana et al., 2023) Stating that the independent curriculum and the 2013 curriculum have been developed based on the objectives of the National Education System, which is to educate students to develop religious attitudes, intelligence, and noble character. In the 2013 curriculum, the methods used in learning include four methods, which are *scientific approach, inquiry, discovery, project based learning and cooperative learning* (Maro, 2013). Whereas (Fitriani, 2023) mentions that in the Merdeka curriculum, students are encouraged to work on project-based activities, they will complete learning based on real life. With this, students will apply their knowledge and critical thinking in completing

projects based on real life problems. All learning methods certainly have negative and positive outputs, as do both curricula. The same challenge in both curricula lies with the teachers. Teachers feel burdened by the demands of rapid implementation of the new curriculum, while the necessary support and training are still inadequate, showing that a curriculum transition without proper planning and training can hinder teacher performance, especially in terms of teaching readiness and the ability to adapt to student needs (Amanda et al., 2025).

In this era of Society 5.0, education systems in developed and developing countries have undergone changes. Similarly, in Indonesia, curriculum changes have been made with the hope of improving and finding a better system than before. (Satiyorini & Setiawan, 2023) stating that education in Indonesia is still a concern, as can be seen from the ranking data from Human Development Index. Among 174 countries in the world, Indonesia ranked 102nd (1996), 99th (1997), 105th (1998), and 109th (1999). This shows that the quality of human resources in Indonesia is declining. The government should be able to adjust the concept of education to be more mature by paying attention to existing internal and external problems. Inconsistent curriculum changes have an impact on students and teachers as bridges of information (Ritonga, 2018). The implementation of student-centered learning with the aim of honing students' critical thinking skills began in the 2013 Curriculum (Maro & Nurbatra, 2013). Unfortunately, the results in the field are still unsatisfactory. Some teachers who are not yet ready cannot maximize this method, which ultimately causes their teaching techniques to revert to teaching-centered techniques, where teachers act as the sole source of information and students tend to sit quietly and listen. Usually, students are only required to memorize material and then use it to answer questions that have been given. This is good for students' short-term memory, but when faced with real-world problems, they may not be able to solve them. Therefore, the learning model needed by students in the 0.5 society era needs to be given serious consideration.

In the 21st century, students need the ability to solve real-life problems, namely those encountered in society outside of school, which cannot be solved by simply memorizing material. These skills will be developed through the application of the Authentic Learning method. (Chabeli et al., 2021b) mention that this method involves giving students real-life problems and encouraging them to use HOTS (High Order Thinking Skills) independently. Students will become accustomed to analyzing problems, evaluating information, and producing results. This will hone their critical thinking, creative thinking, communication,

and collaboration skills. In Authentic Learning, students will engage in more hands-on activities, such as role-playing, problem-based learning, case studies, and direct participation in groups (Lombardi & Oblinger, 2015). In Authentic Learning activities, teachers are no longer the sole source of information. Their role has changed to that of facilitators and guides for students in classroom learning activities. Students can express themselves more freely and can collaborate and convey their ideas with greater confidence (Chabeli et al., 2021a).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This article formulates the problem based on the many learning methods that exist in the world of education. Authentic learning, as one of them, has a learning model that is needed by students in the 21st century. With the change in the curriculum in Indonesia, which is considered to lack thorough preparation in its implementation and the variety of methods used in it. The hope is to create competitive human resources, but the output in the field that we can see is apparently different from the expectations of the government and educators. This raises the question, will the Authentic Learning model be effective if applied to the curriculum in Indonesia, considering that many developed countries have implemented this method, such as Finland, Japan, and the United States?. This article will compare the Authentic Learning method with other methods that also focus on student activity in learning. PJBL and PBL are project-based methods that focus on encouraging students' critical thinking, problem-solving, effective communication, teamwork, creativity, and innovation skills (Lubis et al., 2024).

METHOD

This study was written using a qualitative approach and employed a literature review method. As mentioned by (Creswell, 2009) in (Wahyudi et al., 2019) A method of gathering information through activities conducted by researching literature, books, journals, and institutional archives. This article is written based on journal sources, for example, in analyzing the concept of understanding the Authentic Learning method, which can be referenced from (Bick Har, 2005). It is explained that Authentic Learning is a method that provides complex problems based on real-life issues with student participation being prioritized in learning. It is mentioned by (Chabeli et al., 2021b) that Authentic Learning

activities will be carried out through collaboration, discussion, and problem solving focused on real-world issues. This will hone higher-order thinking skills, creativity, communication, and problem solving, with teachers acting only as facilitators. In addition, the concepts used to understand the differences between the curricula currently used in Indonesia were obtained from (Martatiyana et al., 2023) and (Maro, 2013). This approach is commonly used in scientific research because it allows researchers to obtain and utilize data that has been collected and published by other individuals in the past (Lubis et al., 2024). The presentation of data obtained from information through literature review methods is compiled narratively to draw conclusions as a form of analysis results (Wahyudi et al., 2019).

DISCUSSION

1. Definition

Descartes, a 16th-century philosopher, argued that everyone thinks and acts according to their inner moral voice and is responsible for their actions. Several years later, the philosopher Rousseau supported Descartes' view that everyone has morality and authenticity within themselves. Furthermore, a philosopher named Herder argued that human existence is recognized when people are able to channel their creativity, and this idea was later used as the definition for the Authentic Learning method (Bick Har, 2005). In the KBBI, the word authentic can be interpreted as genuine, true, real, and trustworthy. Thus, authentic learning can be understood as a learning process carried out using methods and in environments that correspond to the “real” experiences in students' lives, both inside and outside the classroom (Lestari, 2018b). In authentic learning methods, the required environment must be multidisciplinary in nature, for example, designing a container for a specific purpose, setting rules, planning a budget, and solving a crisis. Authentic learning is closely related to real-life problem tasks, in which students will be busy with practical work rather than mere memorization. Based on the (Bick Har, 2005) journal about the definition and basic concepts of Authentic Learning, it is written that this method has 11 characteristics, as follows:

- **Characteristic of *Authentic Learning* :**

1. **Real-world relevance:** This means that learning activities given to students must be rooted in real-life situations and contexts.

2. **Teacher as facilitator:** Educators are tasked with providing motivation, task guidance, timelines, resources, and support to students in completing their tasks.
3. **Engages all the senses of learners:** Provides opportunities for students to think, feel, conceptualize, and act to find solutions.
4. **Interdisciplinary:** Encourages students to hone their skills so they can be applied in real-life contexts.
5. **Complex, sustained tasks:** Provides complex tasks with the expectation that students will spend time honing their intellectual abilities.
6. **HOTS development:** Independent learning that encourages students to solve problems using C4, C5, and C6 skills in Bloom's taxonomy, such as analyzing, identifying, and searching for information sources that are relevant or irrelevant to the goal of solving a problem.
7. **Collaborative:** Used in completing tasks and training students to convey information, interact with friends, and develop cooperation skills.
8. **Value-laden:** Learning activities that provide opportunities for students to reflect on and integrate personal beliefs during the learning process.
9. **Tangible and authentic products:** At the end of the learning process, students can create products or results that can be useful for the community in real-life situations.
10. **Authentically assessed:** The learning evaluation process is carried out in a way that reflects real-life assessment methods.
11. **Creative outcomes:** The results can be diverse and innovative, not just focused on predetermined procedures.

2. Comparison

To find out more about whether Authentic Learning will be effective if applied as a learning method in the Indonesian curriculum. Here, a table will be presented showing the learning stages of the Authentic Learning method with two other methods that are familiar in the application of learning in the independent curriculum and K-13. These two methods focus on activity and encourage the intellectual qualities of students that will be needed in the 21st

century, namely the PBL (Problem Based Learning) and PJBL (Project Based Learning) methods. When understood at a basic level, these three well-known methods appear very similar, so the table below will provide further explanation of the comparison by looking at the differences in the stages of learning. The stages of implementing PJBL learning are sourced from the paper (Afriana, 2015) , PBL (Masrinah et al., 2019), and Authentic Learning based on (Bick Har, 2005). Through this comparison, readers can understand the key characteristics that distinguish the three methods in terms of objectives, steps, and learning direction. In addition, this stage serves as a basis for evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of Authentic Learning when implemented in the current Indonesian educational environment.

Table 1. Differences in the Learning Stages of AL, PJBL, and PBL.

No.	Authentic Learning	PJBL	PBL
1.	Setting the senario	Start with essential question	Giving the problem
2.	Re-defining the task and iquiry	Design project	Students make a discussion
3.	Accomplishing the task	Create schedule	Searching information/ data
4.	Presentation	Monitoring the students and progress of project	Solving the problem
5.	Evaluation	Assess the outcome	Presentation
6.		Evaluation th experience	Evaluation

In the third stage of learning using these methods, it can be seen that learning begins with the presentation of material in accordance with the context of each method. The next activity is to work on or find solutions to existing problems. Then, the learning activity will continue with the presentation of the results obtained by the students, which will be followed by an evaluation or feedback where the teacher will comment on the results they have achieved. Other students can also provide corrections or comments on their friends' assignments. That way, the more input they receive, the broader their perspective on a problem will be. In addition, when students are independent in analyzing a complex problem, they will tend to actively ask questions, which will lead to discussion as their critical thinking skills begin to

be developed (Anwari et al., 2015). Next, we will discuss the advantages and disadvantages of each method to truly compare whether the Authentic Learning method can be applied to the current situation in Indonesia. The sources for each method are obtained from several journals, such as the PBL method, which is referenced from (Masrinah et al., 2019), PJBL method from (Afriana, 2015), and AL is sourced from (Valvona & Yoneda, 2018).

Table 2. Advantages of AL, PJBL, and PBL Methods.

No.	AL	PJBL	PBL
1.	Provides a positive impact on increasing student motivation.	Increases student motivation to continue exploring a subject in greater depth.	Student centered.
2.	Provides information about real-life issues.	Becomes more active in solving complex problems.	Improves students' problem-solving skills
3.	Learning is tailored to the needs of 21st-century students.	Develops communication skills.	Encourages students to explore a subject in greater depth in order to solve problems.
4.	This teaching method is more effective than other learning methods.	It trains students' skills in searching for information sources.	It hones critical thinking and scientific thinking.
5.	Improves students' ability to convey and receive information.	Provides students with experience in organizing projects, time management, and negotiation.	Improves students' social and communication skills.
6.	Students are more independent in finding learning resources.	Opportunities for students to develop.	Acquires skills in time management, focus, data collection, report preparation, and evaluation.

Table 3. Disadvantages of AL, PJBL, and PBL Methods.

No.	AL	PJBL	PBL
1.	Requires more time to complete tasks.	Requires a lot of time to complete projects.	Teachers' difficulties in changing their teaching style.
2.	Limited materials or tools that are suitable for real-world tasks.	Requires considerable costs.	Requires more time to solve problems.
3.	It is difficult to assess each student objectively because the tasks given are subjective and varied.	Teachers face obstacles in adapting to changes in learning methods.	Students will either complete the task early or late.
4.	The gap in access to technology for some students.	The large amount of equipment that must be provided.	Requires more in-depth data, information, or research.
5.	Some students are not yet familiar with this method.	Students who are weak at gathering information will find it difficult.	It is quite difficult to assess learning.
6.	Poorly designed learning will frustrate students and cause them to fall behind.	It is possible that students will be less active in groups.	
7.		There is concern that differences in topics between groups will prevent other groups from fully understanding each other's topics.	

When we examine the advantages and disadvantages of these three methods, it is clear that Authentic Learning is superior because of its relevance to the real world, its ability to foster motivation to learn, and its alignment with the competencies needed in the 21st century. However, this does not mean that the other two methods are not in line with what students

need today, given the differences in their learning focus. PBL focuses on achieving targets through activities such as designing, testing, or implementing a product or project. In contrast, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) incorporates more dominant constructivist principles because it provides more space for exploration, creativity, in-depth investigation, and requires students to take control of their learning process independently (Roach et al., 2018). These three methods have similar general shortcomings, particularly in terms of time allocation, teacher preparation, and the complexity of the assessment system. Therefore, determining the ideal learning method should take into account the needs of students, their level of readiness, and the facilities available at the school. Every method used will inevitably have challenges in its implementation, and Authentic Learning is no exception.

Experts are trying to figure out how humans learn and what teaching methods are needed in this era. How does a student transform information into long-term knowledge that can be used again in a relevant way. (Lombardi & Oblinger, 2015) mentions that there are three principles of Authentic Learning that can support experts' findings in analyzing how humans learn:

- 1). Students looking for connection : This means that students tend to find it easier to digest new material if it is personally relevant to them. If the information provided is unfamiliar to students, they tend to find it more difficult to accept.
- 2). Long-lived attachments come with practice: Knowledge can be truly absorbed if it is applied repeatedly and associated with various actions, locations, and individuals. Without practice, these knowledge attachments will slowly fade from memory.
- 3). New contexts need to be explored: The human brain tends to store information through social aspects that are familiar to them, such as places, actions, and individuals around them. Therefore, the material needed by students should be centered on existing events.

Through additional differentiators, Authentic Learning involves complex communication such as persuading, explaining, conveying, and negotiating in complex problem solving through collaboration (Lombardi & Oblinger, 2015). With this, Authentic Learning excels in providing what students need to prepare them for real life in the 21st century. In addition, one of the important roles in 21st century learning is the role of technology. Apart from the ability to deal with complex problems in the outside world, students should be able to keep up with

technological developments. In this era, competition in finding suitable jobs requires soft skills. To be able to blend in with society, we must learn. Therefore, educators must be able to provide space for students to express their opinions and questions. Students will ultimately be encouraged to innovate and create according to the needs of the 21st century. They should be honed to improve their fluency of thinking, flexibility, elaboration, and elabority (Baya Tamin et al., 2022).

3. Implementation

The use of Authentic Learning methods has certainly begun to be implemented in several subjects or institutions. The implementation of Authentic Learning takes into account the readiness of teachers, students, and the facilities available at the school. In the journal (Astuti, 2018) Explaining the use of the Authentic Learning method in the print media production course in the Educational Technology study program at IKIP Mataram. Mentioning that with the use of the Authentic Learning method in this course, students are actively able to complete a booklet project in line with the theme they have chosen. (Astuti, 2018) mention that the students were assigned specific tasks in the project, and they were responsible for completing their respective tasks. The project was carried out in groups, where students were encouraged to discuss with each other between groups as well as with lecturers. At this stage, they will use and hone their communication skills, information transfer, information reception, and how to work in groups. This trains them to acquire 21st-century skills that can be used in the future for work and social interaction. From these results, it can be understood that the use of authentic learning provides many benefits for students.

- First, students can learn more actively.
- Second, they gain experience working in groups to complete a project.
- Third, students can learn directly by creating a product that can later be used as learning material in school.
- Fourth, complete difficult tasks that require high-level thinking skills, such as analyzing, compiling, designing, processing, and evaluating information for project purposes.
- Fifth, students can develop social and discussion skills, both within teams and with other groups.
- Sixth, they learn to be disciplined and responsible for the tasks assigned to them.

In Indonesia, the application of the Authentic Learning concept is reflected in a number of studies that indicate its ability to improve the quality of learning activities, from primary education to higher education. An example of the use of this method is revealed in a study on authentic learning in the preparation of descriptive texts undertaken by (Lestari, 2018a). This study found that students still have difficulty writing because previous learning only presented light tasks that were not challenging enough and did not provide opportunities for students to observe real objects directly. Through the application of Authentic Learning, students are involved in observation, exploration, and analysis of objects that are relevant to their lives, so that they are able to explore information more deeply and develop ideas creatively. This method has been proven effective in improving higher-order thinking skills, such as analyzing, evaluating, and producing more detailed, innovative, and meaningful descriptive texts. These findings confirm that authentic learning provides a more contextual and relevant learning experience, which in turn can encourage students to be more active and participate in the teaching and learning process.

In the realm of modern Indonesian education, this approach is highly relevant to the Merdeka Curriculum, which emphasizes contextual learning, differentiation, and strengthening the Pancasila Student Profile. Authentic Learning provides opportunities for educators to design learning activities that focus on real experiences, collaboration, investigation, and creative products that can be presented to audiences outside the school environment. Therefore, the implementation of Authentic Learning is not only relevant to Indonesian language subjects, but can also be applied in various other subjects that require observation, analysis, and presentation of results. However, its successful implementation still requires support from adequate facilities, teacher readiness, and authentic and accurate assessment strategies.

CONCLUSION

In comparing Authentic Learning, PJBL, and PBL methods, it can be seen that the three methods are almost the same, but their learning focus is different. Authentic Learning focuses on solving real-life problems outside the classroom, PJBL focuses on project design and implementation, while PBL focuses on analysis and data exploration to solve a problem. (Murniyati & Winarto, 2018) explaining the use of PJBL and PBL methods can equally improve problem-solving skills, making students more active and directly involved in

learning. All three aim to develop HOTS (High Order Thinking Skills), which is a higher-level thinking process that includes critical, analytical, synthetic, and creative thinking activities. These three methods encourage students to think critically because they will try to solve problems, make decisions, evaluate assumptions, and seek information based on data or information (Cholily & Eriyanti, 2022). Seeing that the implementation of PJBL and PBL methods is effective for application in Merdeka Curriculum learning, there is also a great opportunity for the implementation of the Authentic Learning method to be accepted and carried out effectively, similar to the learning experiences using the PBL and PJBL methods. This can be seen from the similarities in the advantages of the three methods in the table above, as well as the harmonious learning stages in the three methods.

In implementing a learning method in a curriculum, there are certainly many things to consider. The transition from the old method that teachers and students are accustomed to using to a new method should not be rushed. In an era filled with technological advances and social change, the world of education faces many complicated and complex challenges in meeting the demands of the 21st century. (Isma et al., 2023) mentions that problems in Indonesian education lie in the uneven distribution and low quality of school infrastructure, including physical facilities and infrastructure; problems with educators, including the quality of educators, low welfare and support for teachers, and a lack of training and professional development opportunities; the quality and relevance of the curriculum, which lacks relevance to real-world issues, is out of step with industry needs, lacks character and soft skills development, and is inconsistent. All methods will be effective in learning if there is a balanced learning environment and a curriculum that includes the development of competencies and skills in line with educational objectives and student needs (Munfiatik, 2023). This will help students to be better prepared to enter society.

In facing the challenges of Indonesia's still unsatisfactory educational conditions, the government should act with careful preparation. Existing problems should be immediately addressed in the mission to provide a proper education for Indonesian children. The need to become more active and efficient in the future requires careful evaluation to understand the impact of these changes (Sinuraya et al., 2024). We need a way that not only improves teaching methods, but also improves the skills of teachers, enhances facilities and infrastructure, and increases student motivation to learn (Kurniawati, 2022). Authentic Learning addresses students' needs in preparing themselves to become individuals who can survive and innovate in the 21st century. The main focus of Authentic Learning in outdoor

learning or focusing on real-life problems will be greatly needed for students today. With proper implementation and consistent policy support, Authentic Learning can be a solution to improve the quality of education in Indonesia. Therefore, it can be concluded that Authentic Learning is relevant and effective to be applied in the Indonesian curriculum, especially in preparing the young generation of Indonesia to face real challenges in the world.

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